

Computing few values

Computing few values of my function $f(n)$ and $g(n)$ python code by AI
but the function is by me

$$f(1) = (\pi + 1)^{29}$$

```
main.py +
1 import mpmath as mp
2 import sys
3 import time
4
5 sys.set_int_max_str_digits(1000000) # allow up to 1 million digits
6
7 # Set precision very high so matches are stable
8 mp.mp.dps = 5000
9
10 def find_exponent(target, precision=3000):
11     """
12     Increase exponent n until (pi+1)^n contains the string 'target'.
13     Reports how many exponents were checked and how long it took.
14     """
15     n = 1
16     checked = 0
17     start_time = time.time()
18
19     while True:
20         val = mp.power(mp.pi + 1, n)
21         s = mp.nstr(val, precision) # string representation with fixed precision
22         checked += 1
23
24         # Print progress every 1000 checks with elapsed time
25         if checked % 1000 == 0:
26             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
27             print(f"Checked {checked} exponents so far... (n={n}, elapsed {elapsed:.2f}s)")
28
29         if target in s:
30             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
31             print(f"Total exponents checked: {checked}")
32             print(f"Elapsed time: {elapsed:.2f} seconds")
33             return n, val
34
35     n += 1
36
37 # Interactive loop
38 while True:
39     target = input("Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): ")
40     if target == "0":
41         break
42     n, val = find_exponent(target, 3000)
43     print(f"Found '{target}' in (pi+1)^{n}")
44     print(f"Exponent n = {n}")
45     print(f"Value = {val}\n")
46
```

TERMINAL PROBLEMS

```
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 3.
Total exponents checked: 29
Elapsed time: 0.04 seconds
Found '3.' in (pi-1)^29
Exponent n = 29
Value = 790412986133767843.01464135400432552035043522901157274273936528407200199460414260782838408092985512314430898753688393831
74167670256931154221732079724884954865314778098638774549783995599680078297671371681439501848302164735061864229762864351155758615
31736818800072498888958036186253686368589585049351668728177457975412230356613705437213893988053298309661375607213158617735390920
5175672876189819051932711260850462322637703605282200363501223217333479903491288822606383012127675919902762207497960198616568939
1156710619353689659025158008326106978925180107097730644622692089373090238647174641184247895425934175623883663368997144525654251
537763782670834080982678817389056757721647633536545793229537934800335443347173956066743714210806264876237680258449124208082171447
47248277307622457861848712872488696018789400275035707841962323210963485954294093746740622903152579820756580616155615569634207049
0835162750771561710048875139050547061140510094649473384227983420028467331535260496565199254426279707874603480820766258583310337
41887429947945519485012406964536826701245134447838517237646276170551969651882221608442618137904826721286313292332178252775431574
17239212020440075790515167125549274101490335481427585720393900560305276301894569536032266886904772369563364027410643314211021926
58204406434957786408200420185251056336983366970554325832065037691708852619177987997147668202183918319091037766832386131326594138
13749467092568099677544214983122724044501347277838671163961755972222775805794506693872909128158563116060608736353190438143195084
44528832644739780102198138641909781111776328472862023162661077613268338026194157958605582097394929676562923057423969215895631018
7091910939358064736956425098571907232848946355348894296675758832484930092518380056331620969405889711709883199813599892572438442
79924932215538292722233470153093194056700673965136490366561450672166367738873600609817356484592626521596164615988405122574146
6611929077151765123923052038344888106114589691227869733628034950578131733208730728845402888588527400681516415592705644531627506
1615699807355510966338290483929102314526144321289248630267924562567842938936688772087390665458254505376160249075769678885173895
97907246235239406391335078538181127750479016549827581432385085223647707181471640725588694504239583281441878092224562499590165
2741496888655131789360049209859321944949908196588319715921462090606283420675917164009575627011918670035961620552393135128805757
150106897852633216953537195939783696012964749929409358254889942029232481648015518623002169207587427542058950561532207052171654
7385665423267582044896434141003596356752259515130372012845121637594254863368597423463563300014483035516185919478405953268029539
083240441227279104902271208358467672875303178520561470238583547621889432121801947871897725543785326112591323578820581619800939
52600424528663613273127089048915001057760510244286184655464884768333329145493875740983693793483078336270951662360349946240013
065321836242894819201580570188481116107655900866719869203118619992755428051469112521371152762061053415991629611145085827271325
39785673078868152543514862654633017668317407366348466900955373162516207469415697730549701411028332565936028122797052750423247639
9673553621798193479214627567544363700315982909483535624615525365292823195043468483854725272829081030015094718324154309577164878
3728513043326203241507431108197791934994084065543616347359459782127148929872274790611804786113142563525941438312196753557146639
225686391505917823337442426544431447001530963959770331561734371564922420402398226318020058235247492752332621225184209391
3695164074128811136277889736279254017240128766263352416050440529533097053388354270766464382815207203045117794420116443427158838
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308869895370562450136708280847386994895423405864314422641765263489554001080950334201629983380794457573021936605951646080806193
20493899706724177893070883618931877606952427753545894481983831367553246337286875282975248766916424718399224829614724380384691
486994068829180350418551154295706050730999812315946139051482168952583194254039356625761716742195028213387570868200184813516368
2518577439987597879969855034888384290161522675225539009496481925290949531605650025029763723175098515634196913974754075916031416
9033926384323217652152417511652740731520182202015468389391208513800062443998673730800221777172903071632989966293049648066137684
5640974328376713592204318716365484493391154611862583911506618843544109961668256255329468552396844936190840
3364577245665373182880817400868439209342029635005565595453730352934559766255001171458337915032946657832319087253057096119795
525262761453531447677325737542042430738782032213912208441200910223992077165865870740459409186243697719124575347463632040975374
245064881484634692956813272937511292165156789267831425930406450292561839707535333864927244939016560339624440183882471232305613
39271142259716491
```

Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit):

$$f(2) = (\pi + 1)^{72}$$

```
main.py +
1 import mpmath as mp
2 import sys
3 import time
4
5 sys.set_int_max_str_digits(1000000) # allow up to 1 million digits
6
7 # Set precision very high so matches are stable
8 mp.mp.dps = 5000
9
10 def find_exponent(target, precision=3000):
11     """
12     Increase exponent n until (pi-1)^n contains the string 'target'.
13     Reports how many exponents were checked and how long it took.
14     """
15     n = 1
16     checked = 0
17     start_time = time.time()
18
19     while True:
20         val = mp.power(mp.pi - 1, n)
21         s = mp.nstr(val, precision) # string representation with fixed precision
22         checked += 1
23
24         # Print progress every 1000 checks with elapsed time
25         if checked % 1000 == 0:
26             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
27             print(f"Checked {checked} exponents so far... (n={n}, elapsed {elapsed:.2f}s)")
28
29         if target in s:
30             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
31             print(f"Total exponents checked: {checked}")
32             print(f"Elapsed time: {elapsed:.2f} seconds")
33             return n, val
34
35     n += 1
36
37 # Interactive loop
38 while True:
39     target = input("Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): ")
40     if target == "0":
41         break
42     n, val = find_exponent(target, 3000)
43     print(f"Found '{target}' in (pi-1)^{n}")
44     print(f"Exponent n = {n}")
45     print(f"Value = {val}\n")
46
```

```

[Stop] [Share] [Debug] Command Line Arguments
TERMINAL PROBLEMS
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 3.1
Total exponents checked: 72
Elapsed time: 0.11 seconds
Found '3.1' in (pi-1)^72
Exponent n = 72
Value = 272930126472879573137346885956839755911192533.18378074587519857321926730198256448893728537898785892314567498296526340272
92537118742624344454950846292341408046534520831629841249878549400169349615891268675440310011922395028752808428017486281948286158
762955272345687719075674061278964535675274200144439502445727282513126416767099321086125750606766695671412485789014741671682173
1861007817697994271477051227864249375549912126960379531768275774062508039423683497354075780300443447957817938625900422412052515
331213394684519604388832131184306471102043995714945922498140755766252985479346132567438959255136176512212325527262969839124508
0170461021922047288864974080631677628236951154143235132106163425677808908140901528417388511605302086746839179998537455903232732
06187078622529484800853937907846645851608038255834017869534991267208769678043086510171969080706499606091527490846323581607320364
7148343324084839204762064233841869213201876706640121618636301595019128815240771238663426486380399292837758897427054385114856887
1334122746648279301519381061897271601885020730864776940430310337082965941236977675641284513857344885476206496944227684856708928
70376461842131187126796908714606597086969523762153786456580987763494204706829891520732063793108934292376638337204572247525787531
59983135673347220450786109203590317964384861627159806918823908576808658932666273282158951524208701755493199590131194946840507967
177424763761146897395640392507653210499278564975803539858441636216723279792828327400541518788582013126883573605360033260452471
614453499289075381061148021327034280429825523508720818821519374073114900991421967298694842093411873747372753572254658540005291
46568191513181256004610068227437685204133455827712618805791197711660672009096320640573469808172556650151532650244468902209263738
19621108826410629745804508065344084260008946480037975734357249696453198926436851004478309861889895359277535635390743405314489
73225132616986615283075815030152841519138686691664298860656960524506465291162600041195991957817146094217613981440731660580911736
048690188499820805256818945510042268321060453392282841777724451297836068978995937048494609615240243766588094079392851836169207
021100749580663953768390823022083455428402508770606163081058708455265364583365486559420357521802326405365559764314126612690171346
9843091822072639794269893192989569869047077498637607866221409904217608815670584675555975041243460289164176136308742817163633932
564651588383233236485861298389984953188787555906542509837465918725268349872051051189916906440621702817435964843865251327035995
71663310468789155456091979372966980727668099215456830184767397274696483741236761710658309333302676258046992160048495530035773
75712502833780493565302283500092797434593432692786395054112406518386543077296430896791839179163201207356287354841952809767665
482434164823749439980444089743093692485249603233135025299097371698892268635673852878535981627372168950292602241453274366081892
39170808615191318144696840085109624235704272497735119526983714368658417762178905242525342512188724107546995371595542380124043339
02821946034901713878768069565443996500360041920768456688634086911719779219420357242141120347614290607891992800651138054100191
36997233380186124492367494205283868130133573500623275924450810826238308557912464332343169073446525476770998995008942163800360556
8595443630071470872826409267787286909425923978111051597096148187211470770324905635417396234796483678149309292306937347393360520
06166593828563982484605367507430977798996189845466746177533900994605151276589825252917212216718583203964509302862797619041151711
92740729720911854775252838529279432755479216712307943855166065624706666380902534564069582292334913322416947590723346223743511029
520714680105522771382254122447011302484797034637773984065893363959212531106069211153228288456706719571531676312677067643205511
35834940862390637994602226151160949078340149973163912602327122072478916955144508993171841630840535871458324609526660832460667
4191512588625046969214571078919962019934091846635050303304754140371480922972545014050164360143670181500221676130713057436676511
2491783731801249139143103877766655636138119992771693866796958467860651192218276980634533814927814514700858067112802809977467847
1283731980628472159532045312221907100515725648315738191865329139665513972116473385874656289058297066632912968207812210541064490
3169938951405195246042035821041190452987903747928840529881264042254436916060486503143251079656452595452994765618505015135941
91799349664623542013971858170997721357010855617911458191633097873808686556919087395182920022175829022176806624645384968
036599066716302046013803135560901161040802687533182709117367759473566671522074057375742586055728790745964620436712112001882084
5694693805823998191465976111985322475210737644662323083556585047835377220869066637510963099766069839290657519084754170212
0359608611206053739083452652563312060592025780251792603738422725891111038793770740439581611758129253595432278457818279640355976
86551525121770910
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit):
```

$f(3)=(\pi+1)^{621}$ (*Warning: using low precision here will give wrong answers using high precision eg:30000;50000 takes longer to search 47.31 seconds instead of shown image*)

```
main.py +
1 import mpmath as mp
2 import sys
3 import time
4
5 sys.set_int_max_str_digits(1000000) # allow up to 1 million digits
6
7 # Set precision very high so matches are stable
8 mp.mp.dps = 5000
9
10 def find_exponent(target, precision=3000):
11     """
12     Increase exponent n until (pi+1)^n contains the string 'target'.
13     Reports how many exponents were checked and how long it took.
14     """
15     n = 1
16     checked = 0
17     start_time = time.time()
18
19     while True:
20         val = mp.power(mp.pi + 1, n)
21         s = mp.nstr(val, precision) # string representation with fixed precision
22         checked += 1
23
24         # Print progress every 1000 checks with elapsed time
25         if checked % 1000 == 0:
26             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
27             print(f"Checked {checked} exponents so far... (n={n}, elapsed {elapsed:.2f}s)")
28
29         if target in s:
30             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
31             print(f"Total exponents checked: {checked}")
32             print(f"Elapsed time: {elapsed:.2f} seconds")
33             return n, val
34
35     n += 1
36
37 # Interactive loop
38 while True:
39     target = input("Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): ")
40     if target == "0":
41         break
42     n, val = find_exponent(target, 3000)
43     print(f"Found '{target}' in (pi+1)^{n}")
44     print(f"Exponent n = {n}")
45     print(f"Value = {val}\n")
46
```

```
TERMINAL PROBLEMS
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 3.14
Total exponents checked: 621
Elapsed time: 1.22 seconds
Found '3.14' in (pi+1)^621
Exponent n = 621
Value = 1823660470081531791924486508008792643331450110522578750538691823260617254400381961689256649670820380979286920521840447179
896966050731627073410121003867384227887269646326377408860920582853985833491324732374099844375072769214707440712434755821898903594
217786005225335367709388958337818177752489359218148380775171340554634019477308764283063906308164809569261505859365229390619216
67747633.1418597556646646153642770287287931126618278031860223854548495545297282269385017775592557067885662170388194625066289425
10478123102640011211050838364224624321207245005819077556627054379563605221997003999656398793332389980329415049070692027557966044
47611367109626487292536405765693562200271667472805750322806719279955768067649630795916836170887509841611063920601619952546617340
7179441652862969125828074568747396001107192001566836524292646925795786305755960173558301015962375529005456611651185217757477710
13284676657107173938086134365153015892099978634904523032854731802572660614895669607023723498001020443925696714712248904564333845
3914337466109314976585007653691960890149338708085499677738057450693682592590198310609654554967995925933599567837626203341738425
52378909237743195518877592376975502219234045282415850305174781618156437737611380738872003758947210817804549153140713095960613820
5074107685817016276048763043204694816994574476026451675816791171834569450524273743258960346272284247637978248752458674292067620
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3322189804759438853324284940827510751522590992189328819916565056372604342367645650037481726247177365825373695475756963828612830
45654810821707805347058602639585739952131110296123345772097908301483390727470083250405025027056629022649821326644456726361836952
3431526032594935352316346620545631512618450958768700607012940413315399475462109168060656177616338476433372130371928192078978858
74014687102057676062386799474858846668172782478583476335034983660479573935473467031721281590969466524951544368674733314055209381
7057009878338781501525392830225871734707619769001318543569838297594415438768291233613029506060543491810724908060469745019031231
8792592439420862528489209901269255053823303645007540258263604902501277606667685384065220059233032114876306961564224576228400334
9740856812376460060832142005014702582359656885681457432129693510490929990327023750866148326226100575067669731241026212179114019
1964420954666842988375171030771996299556449380079733668927361405124856012199305991526028551166430454984242672600443789129014
7991402382971874662561740880304519498134673369431555207562511930809382447048874171602993729844893442536115400017331540482616395
323359317542399416355406313184024982901525521190140864309693789723718256757326230646708500713062410371106368435035341324383990
412536872480649066596084406776051325170812364263207016219694967086702768291211012389947945600363347211876063705915760282590590
975923607171079528251613289483792261273694339368189546723684527019269325122413771032682136298250074849084569412961606225253823301
08457805824845827278383426335226463803750625051472792059515567205842336605805058723762837242499553974474181345328165638090131587
3898619844009865116509244246698715722982350722450938365329720685227615745693333587859862016651787069145119764457440134701783317
1789779249002146939069781169329695276093596542941751230691061806396496060990696940267531396649043344987965947941417976860053929
4739562310214076677621001659111569499179709813008584615184089224098452521082166374101290078064337516697223578802039211979138721
1396353883092929879974635649535859374552033857148352715487837301315565622475133291879330920922787164674527209060507172506848667
07679442359826065923367708051252493087142401724190670641278143322199059749839339453498148615805795416419113145910453930108177121
71552066222748697291655393736984892929326985773201240132048615402978963416787046993586372451079709946610844237524518683735477121
02528320799042863829523108304101823097186454776095959642282715173172634402936218951005085920038995195844923526783418
406456875650550295922027691376692520881743609936666598067479734887738121821503560742475420070925132927442879507468496165097
020299353822372654129371154231056111468076401985624625315408471914920892215580789303481989255663986310023407824644467101255303211
44151008789543252570247507688003708608818915395985514473391513605948202089934538947386438979509392573834359996612269640766583
1775301856742452012150447511735859898156303075299842251896118623944179219449159972632778099274045752513441195440746101354175449
9239458296923534209833541541337158668324116704994465783370907041328049305368578073520853434180873439923751232734105064652252343
2279702830626063375302620864581520797706033094670235467908177539257090717780988512620548965009462890445931182820581998493988175
29852755529536562
```

```
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 0
```

$f(4) = (\pi + 1)^{621}$ *(Warning: using low precision search here will give wrong answers using high precision eg: 30000; 50000 takes longer to search 47.31 seconds instead of shown image)*

```
main.py +
1 import mpmath as mp
2 import sys
3 import time
4
5 sys.set_int_max_str_digits(1000000) # allow up to 1 million digits
6
7 # Set precision very high so matches are stable
8 mp.mp.dps = 5000
9
10 def find_exponent(target, precision=3000):
11     """
12     Increase exponent n until (pi-1)^n contains the string 'target'.
13     Reports how many exponents were checked and how long it took.
14     """
15     n = 1
16     checked = 0
17     start_time = time.time()
18
19     while True:
20         val = mp.power(mp.pi - 1, n)
21         s = mp.nstr(val, precision) # string representation with fixed precision
22         checked += 1
23
24         # Print progress every 1000 checks with elapsed time
25         if checked % 1000 == 0:
26             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
27             print(f"Checked {checked} exponents so far... (n={n}, elapsed {elapsed:.2f}s)")
28
29         if target in s:
30             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
31             print(f"Total exponents checked: {checked}")
32             print(f"Elapsed time: {elapsed:.2f} seconds")
33             return n, val
34
35     n += 1
36
37 # Interactive loop
38 while True:
39     target = input("Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): ")
40     if target == "0":
41         break
42     n, val = find_exponent(target, 3000)
43     print(f"Found '{target}' in (pi-1)^{n}")
44     print(f"Exponent n = {n}")
45     print(f"Value = {val}\n")
46
```

```

[Terminal]
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 3.141
Total exponents checked: 621
Elapsed time: 1.22 seconds
Found '3.141' in (pi-1)^621
Exponent n = 621
Value = 182366047008153179192448650080792643331450110522578750538691823268617254480381961689256649670820630979286920521840447179
89696605073162707341012100386738422780726964632637748860920582853985833491324732374099844375072769214707440712434755821898903594
2177860052253356770938895833781871777524893592181483807751713405554634019477308764283063906308164809569261505859365229390619216
67747633.141859755664664615364277028728793112661827803186022385454849545297282269385017755592557067885662170388194625066289425
104781231026400112118508383642246243212072450058190775566270547395636052199700399956398795332809980329415049070692025757966044
4761136710962648729253640576569356220027166747280575032200671927995768067649630795916836170887509841611063920601619952546617340
717944165286296912582807456874739600110719200156683652429264692579578630575596017358301015962735529005456611651185217775477710
13284676657187173938886134365153015892099978634904523032854731802572660614895669607023723498001020443925696714712248904564333845
391433746610931497658007653691960890149338708085499677738057450693682592590198310609654554967995925935599567837626203341738425
5237809237743195518877592376975502219234045282415850305174781618156437737611380738872003758947210817804549153140713095796061387
5074107685817016276048763042046948169945744760264516758167911718345694505242737432589603462727284247637978248752458674292067620
08322832937559683551173034641866755541262843160480707551228013218580028831155706353793086048304556512849780348747346720257086808
75383153505406807648039784620713000051858685946234132975471085838980080002935324383351482253252884591248157511147032542884055705
3322189847594388533242849408275107515225909921893288199165650563726043423676456500374817262471773658253736965437569653828612830
456548108217078053470586026395857399521311102961233457720979083014833907274700832504050250705662902264982126644456726361036952
34315260325949353352316346620545631512618450958768700067012940413315399475462109168066561776163384764333721303731928192078978858
740146871020576760623867994748588466681727824785834763350349836604795739354734670317212815990969466524951544368674733314055209381
7057009878338781501525392830225871734707619769001318543569838297594415438768291233613029506060543491810724980860469745019031243
87925924394220862528489209901269255053823303645007540258263604902501277606667685384065220059233032114876306961564224576228400331
97408568123764600608321420050147025823596568856814574732129693510490929990327023758066148326226100575067669731241026212179114019
19644209546668429883757103077199629956544938079733660927361405128456012199305991526028551166430454984242672600443786843709129014
79914023829718746625617408803045194981346733694315552075625119308090382447048874171602993729844893442536115400817331540482616395
32353931754239941635540631318402498290152552119014086430969378972371825675732623064627085002913062410371106368435035341324383990
4125336872480649066596804406776051325170812364263207016219694967086702768291211012389947945600363347321187606370591576028258250959
9759236071710795282516132894837922612736943393681954672368452701926932512241377103268213629825007484908456941296160622523823301
084570858248458272783834242633522646380375062505147279205951556720584233660503055872376283762499553974474181345328165638090113587
3898619844009865116059942424669871572298235072425093836532972068522761574569333587898620166517870691451197644574401347301783317
1789779249802146939069781169329695276093596542941751230691061806396496060906969482675313596849043344987965947941417976600853929
47395562310214076677621001659111569499179709813080584615184089224098452521082166374101290078064337513697223578820309211979138721
1396353883839292928977946356493585937455203385714835271548783730131556562247513329187933092902278716467452720906507172506848667
076794423598260692533677080512524930871424017241906780641278143322199059749839339453498148615805795416419111345910453930108177121
7155206622274869729165539373698489292932698577320124013204861540297896341678704699358637245107970994661084423752451868373547214
025283207990428638295231083041018230971866454776095596422827151731726234402936218951005085749437455392003899519584449235826783418
406456875650550295920277691376692520881743609936666598067479734887773812182150355607424754200709231229274412879507466496165097
02029933822372654129371154231056111468076401985624625315408471914920892155807893034819892556639061800234078246444221253303211
44151008789543252570247507688803770860881891539559851447339151316059482028993543894738643897950939257834359996621269624076683
177530185674245201215044751173585989815630307529984225189611866239441792194491599726327780992740457525134411981440764101354175449
92394582969235342098335415415337158668324116704994465783309970413280493053685780735208534341808734399237512327341056462522343
22797028306260633753026208645815207977060330946702335467900177539257090717780988512620548965009462090445931182820581998493988175
29852755529536562
```

f(5) unfindable with 50000;30000;30000 in the span of roughly 44 minutes 48 seconds up to exponent pf roughly 15000

```
main.py +
1 import mpmath as mp
2 import sys
3 import time
4
5 sys.set_int_max_str_digits(1000000) # allow up to 1 million digits
6
7 # Set precision very high so matches are stable
8 mp.mp.dps = 50000
9
10 def find_exponent(target, precision=30000):
11     """
12     Increase exponent n until (pi+1)^n contains the string 'target'.
13     Reports how many exponents were checked and how long it took.
14     """
15     n = 1
16     checked = 0
17     start_time = time.time()
18
19     while True:
20         val = mp.power(mp.pi + 1, n)
21         s = mp.nstr(val, precision) # string representation with fixed precision
22         checked += 1
23
24         # Print progress every 1000 checks with elapsed time
25         if checked % 1000 == 0:
26             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
27             print(f"Checked {checked} exponents so far... (n={n}, elapsed {elapsed:.2f}s)")
28
29         if target in s:
30             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
31             print(f"Total exponents checked: {checked}")
32             print(f"Elapsed time: {elapsed:.2f} seconds")
33             return n, val
34
35         n += 1
36
37 # Interactive loop
38 while True:
39     target = input("Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): ")
40     if target == "0":
41         break
42     n, val = find_exponent(target, 30000)
43     print(f"Found '{target}' in (pi+1)^{n}")
44     print(f"Exponent n = {n}")
45     print(f"Value = {val}\n")
46
```

Run Share Debug Command Line Arguments

TERMINAL PROBLEMS

```
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 3.1415
Checked 1000 exponents so far... (n=1000, elapsed 105.42s)
Checked 2000 exponents so far... (n=2000, elapsed 240.40s)
Checked 3000 exponents so far... (n=3000, elapsed 417.11s)
Checked 4000 exponents so far... (n=4000, elapsed 608.53s)
Checked 5000 exponents so far... (n=5000, elapsed 759.05s)
Checked 6000 exponents so far... (n=6000, elapsed 958.36s)
Checked 7000 exponents so far... (n=7000, elapsed 1142.47s)
Checked 8000 exponents so far... (n=8000, elapsed 1339.23s)
Checked 9000 exponents so far... (n=9000, elapsed 1507.91s)
Checked 10000 exponents so far... (n=10000, elapsed 1682.45s)
Checked 11000 exponents so far... (n=11000, elapsed 1876.87s)
Checked 12000 exponents so far... (n=12000, elapsed 2087.16s)
Checked 13000 exponents so far... (n=13000, elapsed 2284.74s)
Checked 14000 exponents so far... (n=14000, elapsed 2480.65s)
Checked 15000 exponents so far... (n=15000, elapsed 2687.78s)

KeyboardInterrupt: Execution stopped by user.

** Process exited - Return Code: 130 **
█
```

$p(n)$ same rule but replace all π with e

$$p(1)=(e+1)^6$$

```
main.py +
1 import mpmath as mp
2 import sys
3 import time
4
5 sys.set_int_max_str_digits(1000000) # allow up to 1 million digits
6
7 # Set precision very high so matches are stable
8 mp.mp.dps = 5000
9
10 def find_exponent(target, precision=3000):
11     """
12     Increase exponent n until (e+1)^n contains the string 'target'.
13     Reports how many exponents were checked and how long it took.
14     """
15     n = 1
16     checked = 0
17     start_time = time.time()
18
19     while True:
20         val = mp.power(mp.e + 1, n)
21         s = mp.nstr(val, precision) # string representation with fixed precision
22         checked += 1
23
24         # Print progress every 100 checks with elapsed time
25         if checked % 100 == 0:
26             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
27             print(f"Checked {checked} exponents so far... (n={n}, elapsed {elapsed:.2f}s)")
28
29         if target in s:
30             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
31             print(f"Total exponents checked: {checked}")
32             print(f"Elapsed time: {elapsed:.2f} seconds")
33             return n, val
34
35     n += 1
36
37 # Interactive loop
38 while True:
39     target = input("Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): ")
40     if target == "0":
41         break
42     n, val = find_exponent(target, 3000)
43     print(f"Found '{target}' in (e+1)^{n}")
44     print(f"Exponent n = {n}")
45     print(f"Value = {val}\n")
46
```

```
TERMINAL PROBLEMS
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 2.
Total exponents checked: 6
Elapsed time: 0.01 seconds
Found '2.' in (e-1)^6
Exponent n = 6
Value = 2642.7362695238257009459233086579905835126933313911746379805705760670884853439296236507469753921759832871376679973689343
74442361808998742112524859576558910622346809696927588215443401290735653947001970635280284242086568070914571940667028001047580119
37082893910639361748322810081430354172452359615998470952311830799332515853851942408990558742879249157373630908420777387476130079
24797301048671177528911565395299721388113490380624043071948091174493157568754409455071132455633350980809674181547058007358194540
9111832096142710884355168772082084325574509672947675817055099244875107089901174186367810652383531957007279802981216558476287661
746236062810358853163105127278142653426214359990404084110912753171173993591420192219433871060675696738277212071644024027094532009
20066833770340382235971621864658552143876514443601532943249378212780170433475144293207978850428001956690012023396443125133212648
1452485161654069049811316821635117938098444710831079451002204047767866015126875478212062278327272144690148025783561685327502227
88410668571469527659504268192389253799772640476206944681774048299920901573286678051575937737775209163856540072932981307383979176
45254319431018137426174672036168214667856620065183476961177495031335336425272102596328127108350207009109003053434562914729060634
65087062076792427524004106039673088626929602107688816852253038861009924451355713931284057668610516304250145857574317794874386509
51659132624160481039444373300291847373200100482696906641541054259341776689039023140387363298744304724599057033412481400371805816
765494196845516802203188724292246704239730482620216172219620176904133343909965819217862791892956791715522288162332397549551385
15917413817619847608866595395105912544712383099310635319901342391780238563305110891012701098700112957804223014084523298616732740
4228373079842394688132300504631777354169591502790440089063035084662706446395645502216610152366564613474556866635760479393423234
4695206974308352742445106191288672871434835648327912320798177799574441133604023036303695136229566160080040558426175200788434672
17637820585822844570900571617910913817834966013449785841005436166213788714312781508899175218442127521232774579409719845133580845
08137739598223578803390670536909530155289910273869464789108553983052450683415545285913534287586197030757261476985840038663642064
2560552502960909384118676490785861112972254002375714934377138773844808000143466348539366288973557422423735395289610225328163
68596592533756442100871700494602197429098939289769512003248922846281591526642695579274315744584462587658319601113534107878885
2358603774507531588793327243381688845364539926884760645534508650839873950493209550007317117469298180668675689016701706783174
51832005306887760851998999891938080560346137482077415235001698906031442389543692031559453452743512518207103732112538016552237147
0099061042919890474654093970975460162763406671332253582090754999001500169027259076353112886091774329270502700430144867776581362
64340791460492051160584701480459608463198970337869270418007418822080486186582088735376795106975107653298606784903714656005742621
8153455747078161420976473407362898284500027869185041078509655615443925578676811503511919291872302544646724810479822298614952946
026617763164377946680281853888153744569885965879024617453592677233628532843452635943521724096717568810806817117189063595648710
09246142602126072325011390605931871366909315628462293593996145784637701321666161383276832391198100267315655409134853941185399846
007391913543312413919350243558981302043426074342957872340616881400362235497931278459610674295423801794949143878237299702685137954
01843929514532375762947847358628017814510975702166856834419146725116297849961247985446054337486121223591594963625190707305
9202667750321501791827042648381902902607564951310481484103371492772951506425175866644499023186758457332557585526381411328767532
6181960759009247524739340042937654519351025338755924996106099534100154743653396060129421942219344516079738697371018796075608399
50541830081230165296916297393453456374779427729313859544279643589084117011950403079081741148395014611124619670385078861802252013
97176044173549544101660593743620447997430392938270761455642470697501484898194274711636203309796640489217021450254667965400403726
260851319512646223124666167761444046419220096076030121775275700621884027620854379240390784654945482283100473093371
109343992754653529000841198750255020754818644064638099022256037767641098601142145197947612735868266212372910349523674088675973565
47098265302971822843697326853725204046047169697529409588367952405245121787540564154718201033137606328277516659127422293046
2023555975179327338839469349454039708694165035694510144646804796663365625597490749333014079989800846154248293754288991257828430
5448736820460339538633190235291747974281351798698713690996672483437779349003685622626516225917544837843992171541521495
4782038145994271571652592672209920851583236789920517158064557519856594189589231386581355266136208146572053366654372555387942802
33631769603520604
```

```
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): []
```

$$p(2)=(e+1)^6$$

```
main.py +
1 import mpmath as mp
2 import sys
3 import time
4
5 sys.set_int_max_str_digits(1000000) # allow up to 1 million digits
6
7 # Set precision very high so matches are stable
8 mp.mp.dps = 5000
9
10 def find_exponent(target, precision=3000):
11     """
12     Increase exponent n until (e+1)^n contains the string 'target'.
13     Reports how many exponents were checked and how long it took.
14     """
15     n = 1
16     checked = 0
17     start_time = time.time()
18
19     while True:
20         val = mp.power(mp.e + 1, n)
21         s = mp.nstr(val, precision) # string representation with fixed precision
22         checked += 1
23
24         # Print progress every 100 checks with elapsed time
25         if checked % 100 == 0:
26             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
27             print(f"Checked {checked} exponents so far... (n={n}, elapsed {elapsed:.2f}s)")
28
29         if target in s:
30             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
31             print(f"Total exponents checked: {checked}")
32             print(f"Elapsed time: {elapsed:.2f} seconds")
33             return n, val
34
35     n += 1
36
37 # Interactive loop
38 while True:
39     target = input("Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): ")
40     if target == "0":
41         break
42     n, val = find_exponent(target, 3000)
43     print(f"Found '{target}' in (e+1)^{n}")
44     print(f"Exponent n = {n}")
45     print(f"Value = {val}\n")
46
```

TERMINAL PROBLEMS

```
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 2.7
Total exponents checked: 6
Elapsed time: 0.01 seconds
Found '2.7' in (e-1)^6
Exponent n = 6
Value = 2642.7362695238257089459233086579905835126933313911746379805705760670884853439296236507469753921759832871376679973689343
7444236180899874211252485957655891062234680969692758821544340129073565394700197635280284242086568070914571940667028001647580119
370828939106393617483228100814303541724523596199847095231183079933251585385194240899055874287924915737363090842877387476130079
2479730104867117752891156539529972138811349038062404307194809117449315756875440945567113245563350980809674181547058087358194540
91118320961427108843551687720820843255745096729476758170550992448751070899811741863678106523835319578072798029812116558476827661
74623606281035885316310512727814265342621435999040484110912753171173993591420192219433871060675696738277212071644024027094532009
20066837703403822359716218646585521438765144436015329432493782127800170433475144293207978850428001956690012023396443125133212648
1452485161654069049811316821635117938098444710831079451002204047767866015126875478212062278327272144690148025783561685327502227
8841066857146952765950426819238925379977264047620694468177404829992090157328667805157593773775209163856540072932981307383979176
4525431943101813742617467203616821466785662006518347696117749503133533642527210259632812710835020700910900305343562914729006034
6508706207679242752400410603967308862692960210768881685225303886100992445135571393128405766661051630425014585757431794874386509
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15917413817619847608866595395105912544712383099310635319901342391780238563305110891012701098700112957804223014084523298616732740
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046952069743083527424451061912886728714383564832791232079817779957444113360420363036951362292566160080040558426175208708434672
1763782858582284457090057161791091381783496601344978584108543616621378871431278150899175218444212752123272745794097198451335850845
0813773959822357880339067053690953015528991027386946478910855398305245068341554528591353428758619703075726147698584003863642064
256055285029609093841186764907850611129722540823757149343771387773844080008142663485393366289735574224232735395289610225328163
685965925337356442100871700494602197429098932897695120832489228462815915266426955759274315744584462587658319601131534107787885
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0266176316437794668028185388815374456988596587902461745359267677233628532843452635943521724096717568810806817117189063595648710
092461426021260723250113960605931071366909315628462293593996145784637701321666161383276832391198108267315655409134853941185399846
0073919135433124139193502435589813020434260743429578772340016881400362235497931278459610674372954238017949491438782372072685137954
0184392951453237576294784735862801781451097570216685683441914672511629784996124798544605433748621223591594963625199370519007305
9202667750321501791827642648381902902607564951310481484103371492772951506425175866644499023186758457332557585526381411328767532
6181960799009247524739340042937654193510253387559249961060995345100154743653396060129421942219344151607973869731018796075608395
50541380801230165296916297393453456374779427293138595442796435890804117011950403079081741148395014611124619670385078861802252013
9716704417354954410166059374362044799743032938270761455642470697501484898194274711636203097966404892170214502546679854004803726
26085131951264622312466616776144404641922009607603012177527570802762085437924039078465494548228237096667009203100473939371
1093439927546535290008119875025502075481864406463090922256037767641098601142145979476127350682626812372918349523047088875973565
470982653029718228436973268537252040460471696975294095883679524052542178754056415471820103313706032827516659127396120422929306
202355975179327338839469349454039709869416503569451014464680479666336562559749074933501407998898084615424829375428891257284304
5448736828406339538633190235291747974281351798698713690996876724834377934908368562262651622591830851317544837843992171541521495
478203814599427157165259267622099208515832367899205171580645575198565941095809231386581355266136208146572053366654372555307942802
33631769603520604
```

Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): []

$$p(3) = (e+1)^{332}$$

```
main.py +
1 import mpmath as mp
2 import sys
3 import time
4
5 sys.set_int_max_str_digits(1000000) # allow up to 1 million digits
6
7 # Set precision very high so matches are stable
8 mp.mp.dps = 5000
9
10 def find_exponent(target, precision=3000):
11     """
12     Increase exponent n until (e-1)^n contains the string 'target'.
13     Reports how many exponents were checked and how long it took.
14     """
15     n = 1
16     checked = 0
17     start_time = time.time()
18
19     while True:
20         val = mp.power(mp.e - 1, n)
21         s = mp.nstr(val, precision) # string representation with fixed precision
22         checked += 1
23
24         # Print progress every 100 checks with elapsed time
25         if checked % 1000 == 0:
26             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
27             print(f"Checked {checked} exponents so far... (n={n}, elapsed {elapsed:.2f}s)")
28
29         if target in s:
30             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
31             print(f"Total exponents checked: {checked}")
32             print(f"Elapsed time: {elapsed:.2f} seconds")
33             return n, val
34
35         n += 1
36
37 # Interactive loop
38 while True:
39     target = input("Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): ")
40     if target == "0":
41         break
42     n, val = find_exponent(target, 3000)
43     print(f"Found '{target}' in (e-1)^{n}")
44     print(f"Exponent n = {n}")
45     print(f"Value = {val}\n")
46
```

Terminal Output:

```
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 2.71
Total exponents checked: 332
Elapsed time: 0.62 seconds
Found '2.71' in (e-1)^332
Exponent n = 332
Value = 2257589565529963439639602223059276167012556081041539088014199040800006061556681463448027935451329657464802818591525856514
3900648653336651003906322941422973801785678456435857098306960705834992.716444318831173782371411240273184069509903893083067367144
1112430961253633434216975470900341778712230764691233586912401894785351110119182556679668327923336711601841108189523953298054567
9043172917337758043149701644602729306226945306238419269921022265745012120307985656486815308924135903185450573986627977807478778
03871946286167334668216100222676031705451281698954413983221237471715304254525290849369991108090184361339716356449090542586674781
36033235000351780512771177139733385735944801366252035005939367733593751717407566499092525377689194203929582071411915274090744216
7473476925605849285807559114680254351440473985014332167105901497344876134640780225994775897441540436882515220608055515187600470
18350466813851723699180114654242492780729654690635165427330370413596253498825434192128429190213943957948297192741813886992840067
4571238969425476426935892305243936452462318715656462034051191972948009011057831905182481741294049161024030532911181853431383389
49413857686914658500062459770418084302908102406701926988433317368987328897655205736216440447903814354724624182503212656248468759
91097147997610146633039420745311401343541128628036159628535211574704304822565563894866493658673672126422443769023250962635818
7238886620093859602918873059915110812784483533052000958005781197029342169179023007297086302595458100287786617871844354357911489
834742415548567984559193016584323707530348187668643364568107696769147856832121346747820677824516002209579842512138065032691798
3860911036886629737978907849382582498675760618207401342101304268344482598460986224742692241671723076396817618951437330562444667
43782528613765635874470792117167262549918611205788408482882257879702363221039039759935667566766028547971928299152325967479833407
44226389538176106920422593619706073828472430104538543518054991745526551441456765702025268503269951722015769812289641827348832995
4141630547012658991724290816369253825402037365993010080753328443080477368962710931648778998755134770821467725560396955501129932
2880154476802717352464167806892093831189961665557301126085584200724275982520860928500740929180784468085948941270619272673087846
7240028908373079761742313236016427414624583029122135215644159109272702694746566893482271346501029144918185116541068475266527413
47830864113202374279468359866415493935278276793687530452476841088029988717064958883355465842575855640946493018883124545042156969
7060673538504680251808276312831270101529214044905898455811353708147486378226558694756119607232435638153566988312101267004677121
74483945002080463236713006605395454674473642464943896043514830486696029770005394201789046174501939528369755763733745790877936289
99600740271022749891106410041290078955071653853975607530470842446887908260035762007619097092142017332488941173530928770789503252
7700407864057398693388488820234242468823046314593738873171027590092035716784498433507527378792249595320571836344875513879837
94788145691661865539957563949899312397117105567436385318292385047973551066468911775423736151191212672164567801422625387626459947
903340906312436137657220011976375999454362240720399290515138330695426898078882662268924440882156630856363000093535807133380907
98440808421784850983626582850980303547390064361863535282619375499369497855067869483215921739024217263250151860176228462181099795
15332302441889821383847752723963800802742327479831295628310700045452902673015924652188768412313789490647481929794769634609787205
3550332779114419428705430231593003217294005581239796832189823546200174877117004242683667894521455652090795780745377522445387864
10422888205521924676758821399929423107864888431918805939151928325203792322130902965937112709435398645711872249209569545601170289
457615937649793251617490496163012389426390002758187000899833484166458889152494910770830417214745113271319105643008196824003885
11159956556960455884083422958030093610851627277816604659822994655136431026053281808468353526771490687254091812326336755231787257
930049090450975793718349682583692194281283947782465386542468366005617766214644148670088293769299336688009446461029098927699807
080306533711347090564214892466996875543849691017325481998664435489338691102305800894398153037444239847927610330327380101447205793
54099082494600281483624642409659173831626693362212629808371108985887433874131665615990882319654064375242354886172542635486617254620080
866808966144402058339143256692505891481885593669681064405218713266730469124472285696724841266309810456231304829472024387700912
808163963917625908860596572619874978360610139211379073207627627262789595372732412064857141151938312926176035536583257170344387
5092642060857050490875869938285811074531710883765652314749285154992409374679271601166860245514641025542408160203471771446028
207291909168766956931259558482034540401178376657129027750785808682103876061643254717145531848593602975759220408095194352936483831
30780775105337751
```

Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit):

$p(4)$ unfindable with 50000;30000;30000 in the span of roughly 1 hour
30 minutes 31.46 seconds up to exponent of roughly 12000

```
main.py +
1 import mpmath as mp
2 import sys
3 import time
4
5 sys.set_int_max_str_digits(1000000) # allow up to 1 million digits
6
7 # Set precision very high so matches are stable
8 mp.mp.dps = 50000
9
10 def find_exponent(target, precision=30000):
11     """
12     Increase exponent n until (e+1)^n contains the string 'target'.
13     Reports how many exponents were checked and how long it took.
14     """
15     n = 1
16     checked = 0
17     start_time = time.time()
18
19     while True:
20         val = mp.power(mp.e + 1, n)
21         s = mp.nstr(val, precision) # string representation with fixed precision
22         checked += 1
23
24         # Print progress every 100 checks with elapsed time
25         if checked % 1000 == 0:
26             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
27             print(f"Checked {checked} exponents so far... (n={n}, elapsed {elapsed:.2f}s)")
28
29         if target in s:
30             elapsed = time.time() - start_time
31             print(f"Total exponents checked: {checked}")
32             print(f"Elapsed time: {elapsed:.2f} seconds")
33             return n, val
34
35         n += 1
36
37 # Interactive loop
38 while True:
39     target = input("Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): ")
40     if target == "0":
41         break
42     n, val = find_exponent(target, 30000)
43     print(f"Found '{target}' in (e+1)^{n}")
44     print(f"Exponent n = {n}")
45     print(f"Value = {val}\n")
46
```

Run Share Debug Command Line Arguments

TERMINAL PROBLEMS

```
Enter the string to search for (or 0 to quit): 2.718
Checked 1000 exponents so far... (n=1000, elapsed 99.48s)
Checked 2000 exponents so far... (n=2000, elapsed 229.32s)
Checked 3000 exponents so far... (n=3000, elapsed 446.86s)
Checked 4000 exponents so far... (n=4000, elapsed 633.03s)
Checked 5000 exponents so far... (n=5000, elapsed 790.03s)
Checked 6000 exponents so far... (n=6000, elapsed 1248.34s)
Checked 7000 exponents so far... (n=7000, elapsed 1433.84s)
Checked 8000 exponents so far... (n=8000, elapsed 1635.70s)
Checked 9000 exponents so far... (n=9000, elapsed 2667.94s)
Checked 10000 exponents so far... (n=10000, elapsed 5088.20s)
Checked 11000 exponents so far... (n=11000, elapsed 5263.17s)
Checked 12000 exponents so far... (n=12000, elapsed 5431.46s)

KeyboardInterrupt: Execution stopped by user.

** Process exited - Return Code: 130 **

```